

Basic programming

Exam 1

Q1: Can you provide me a C program in which it writes a triangle rectangle with "*" according to the size given by the user, in which the center is empty? All 3 sides must be the same size (i.e. the same number of "*")

Q2: Can you provide me a C program in which it shows the first 20 deficient numbers?

Q3: Can you provide me a C program in which the user provides you a number and the program converts it to binary?

Exam 2

Q1: Can you provide me a C program in which the array has 50 elements maximum and if there are 3 consecutive identical numbers in the list, it puts the number 0 in the middle? Request a list of numbers at the beginning and display the modified list at the end.

Q2: Can you provide me a C program in which the array has 50 elements maximum, and it develops a function where, starting from a list of numbers, it forms a second list by interspersing zero numbers between the numbers in the initial list? The function returns the size of the new list. Request the original list of numbers, create a second list with this function, and display the second list at the end.

Q3: Can you provide me a C program in which the array has 50 elements maximum and in which indicating whether a list of numbers is balanced (returning 1) or not (returning 0)? A list of numbers will be balanced if the sum of the numbers in opposite positions is always the same. If the list dimension is an odd number, the value of the middle number must be the same of the sum of the last and first values and the rest opposite sum values. If the list contains one value, it is balanced. Request a list of numbers, call the function, and at the end display whether it is balanced or not.

Exam 3

Q1: Can you provide me a C program in which the function makes the following changes to the string passed as a parameter and returns the number of letters passed to lowercase:

Converts 1..9 to 0.

, ; : turns them into .

It turns A..Z into a..z

()[] turns them into !

Let the program ask for a sentence and at the end display the modified sentence and the number of letters changed to lowercase.

Q2: Can you provide me a C program in which the function displays the largest number of consecutive digits in the sentence. Ask for the phrase, call the function and display the result at the end.

Q3: Can you provide me a C program in which the function needs a string as a parameter and in return it deletes repeated characters in the string (leaving only one). Let the program ask for a sentence and display the modified sentence at the end.

Programming

The communication data for each day is being stored in text files named year-month-day.txt, for example today would be 2024-03-25.txt. Each line in the log file contains information about one connection. In the first column the connection time, in the second column the original ip address and finally the protocol type.

10:37 195.184.128.1 DNS

10:38 195.184.128.1 SSH

10:39 195.184.128.1 HTTPS

10:45 205.136.96.4 DNS

10:46 205.136.96.4 HTTP

10:50 195.184.128.1 HTTPS

11:00 205.136.96.4 HTTPS

11:05 200.0.6.44 HTTP

11:10 195.184.128.24 HTTPS

11:12 205.136.96.22 DNS

11:15 205.136.96.22 HTTP

11:18 195.184.128.1 HTTPS

in another file named countries.txt, the network ip corresponding to each country and there is the name of the country.

195.184.128.0 France

205.136.96.0 Spain

197.10.12.0 Portugal

Exam 1

Q1: The first program will be used to identify which country the Web store's customers are from. The program will initially read the countries file to contain its data (country name and ip address). Then the program will offer a menu. The first option in the menu will be to add a new country (the ip and name of the new country).

The second option will be to modify the ip address of a pre-existing country.

The third option will be to display the existing countries once.

The fourth option will be to read a day's worth of traffic data from a file. In this option the program will ask for the name of the traffic file and then load the traffic data.

The fifth option will be to calculate how many HTTPS connections there have been for each country. This function will not only display the data on the screen but also store it in the client.txt file. With the data given before, the result should be the following:

France 4

Spain 1

Portugal 0

Q2: In this section, we will add a new option to the menu. In this case, the functionality to display the countries ordered by the number of connections must be implemented.

Q3: HTTPS connections represent the browsing done by the website users. In this section, the total time spent by each user visiting the website must be calculated. To calculate this time, the user's last connection time of that day is subtracted from the time of the first connection. If a navigation has only one connection, the time is considered to be 0.

Exam 2

Q1: What does the following function calculate? When called from Main, the function will receive an array numbered n. Write and explain the values that function variables have each time during execution.

```
int faa ( int nums [ ], int kop );
int foo ( int a );
int main ( ) {
int zenba kia k []={123 , 523 , 143};
printf ("% i=%i \n " , * zenbakiak , foo ( zenba kia k [ 0 ] ) );
printf ("% i=%i \n " , *( zenba kia k +1 ) , foo ( zenba kia k [ 1 ] ) );
printf ("% i=%i \n " , *( zenba kia k +2 ) , foo ( zenba kia k [ 2 ] ) );
printf ("% i \n " , faa ( zenbakiak , 3 ) );
return 0 ;
}
int faa ( int nums [ ], int kop ){
if ( kop == 1 ){
return foo (*nums ) ;
} else {
return foo (*nums ) + faa ( nums+1 , kop -1 );
}
}
int foo ( int a ){
int b= 0 ;
if ( a < 10 ){
return a ;
} else {
b = a %10 + foo ( a / 10 ) ;
return b ;
}
}
```

Q2: What does the following code do?

```
#define NULL 0
void foo ( int *b , int c , int * a r r , int n );
void blah ( int *r , int s );
int main ( ) {
```

```

int x, y;
int array[5];
int *arr = 0;
arr = array;
if (arr == NULL) {
    exit(1); // should print out nice error msg first
}
x = 10;
y = 20;
printf("x = %d y = %d\n", x, y);
foo(&x, y, arr, 5);
printf("x = %d y = %d arr = %d arr3 = %d\n",
x, y, *arr, *arr+3);
return 0;
}
void foo(int *b, int c, int *arr, int n) {
    int i;
    c = 2;
    for (i = 0; i < n; i++) {
        *(arr+i) = i + c;
    }
    *arr = 13;
    blah(b, c);
}
void blah(int *r, int s) {
    *r = 3;
    s = 4;
}

```

Q3: Write a recursive function that takes two integers a and b as input and returns their greatest common divisor (GCD).

Q4: Develop a recursive function that tells you whether the numbers in an array of integers are ordered from smallest to largest.

Q5: Develop a recursive algorithm for finding a number in an ordered list of numbers.

Exam 3

You need to develop a program to help with elevator maintenance. The purpose of the program is to indicate when maintenance should be carried out based on the trips made by an elevator. To do this, every time the elevator makes a trip, it must save the time of the trip (HH:MM:SS) and the weight of the trip in a list. Knowing that there are 4 meters between the weights, it will be possible to calculate the number of meters traveled by the lift and when it

reaches a certain number of meters (for example 120 meters) we will have to indicate that a maintenance will be required. Elevator maintenance

A function will be called to find out if it should be done or not, which will return the completed meters and also the status of the maintenance (RED TRAFFIC LIGHT if more than 90% of the 120 meters have been completed. ORANGE TRAFFIC LIGHT if the completed meters are between 70% and 90% of the maintenance meters. GREEN TRAFFIC LIGHT if no maintenance is required RED=2, ORANGE=1 and GREEN=0). Once the worker has completed the maintenance of the elevator, by calling a function, delete all trips keeping the last position. In addition, the function will set the meters of movements made by the elevator to 0 and put the maintenance status in green.

Q1: In the first section, the program in C language must do the following.

- (a) Initially a list of trips will be created and the first item in the list will be created manually saying it is at weight 0 and at 00:00:00.
- (b) The program will then simulate some of the moves by adding new trips to the list. Note that the first position of the list will be the element 00:00:00 and weight 0.
- (c) Make and use the function that displays the trips made after simulating a few trips.
- (d) Then carry out and use the function that calculates the meters traveled by the elevator and the maintenance status. To do this, call the functions several times, it will not be necessary to implement a menu.

Q2: In this section you will simulate a maintenance. To do this, delete the entire trip list keeping the last item. The function that will be developed will initialize the number of meters of the routes to 0 and turn the traffic light green.

Q3: Now you have to create a program that manages 3 elevators. For this you will have to define a new data structure, reusing the previous one. Now when adding a new trip you will have to specify the elevator identifier, and when calling the maintenance required function you will have to specify a specific elevator.

Advanced programming

Exam 1

Q1

Develop a Java program using a main class and the necessary classes and methods to develop the following program. The observable pattern Observer or propertyChangeSupport must be used to handle events.

We want to develop an animal tracking system. The programme should do the following:

- Definition of stables or shelters. These will have an identifier, a name and a position (x, y). We will create them by initialising them with the code part denoted below:

```
system.add(new Shelter (1, "Stable", new Position(0,0)));
system.add(new Shelter (2, "Shelter1" , new Position(4,4)));
system.add(new Shelter (3, "Shelter2" , new Position(9,9)));
system.add(new Shelter (4, "Shelter3" , new Position(15,15)));
system.add(new Shelter (5, "Shelter4" , new Position(20,20)));
system.add(new Shelter (6, "Shelter5" , new Position(25,25)));
system.add(new Shelter (7, "Shelter6" , new Position(30,30)));
```

- Register animals. They shall contain at least an identifier and a name.
- Free the animals (at the beginning they will all be in the first shelter, in the Stable) and they will start moving (they will move the same amount on the x and y axis, which will be created randomly). If we select this option, they will be moving all the time until exiting the established limits, in which we will notify that the animal has been lost. Each animal must periodically notify its position so that the farmer knows where they are located.
- Each stable or shelter shall report the number of animals present each time an animal enters or leaves the stable or shelter.
- We will set some limits (limitX and limitY). When the animals go out of the limits, we will stop tracking the animal and we should notify that the animal is lost.
- The animal cannot move to positions $x < 0$ or $y < 0$.

Execution example:

```
1.- Register animals
2.- Free animals (all are set in the first shelter, the Stable.)
0.- Exit
Selection: 1
What is the animal's name? sheep
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:1
1.- Register animals
2.- Free animals (all are set in the first shelter, the Stable.)
0.- Exit
Selection: 1
What is the animal's name? cow
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:2
1.- Register animals
2.- Free animals (all are set in the first shelter, the Stable.)
0.- Exit
Selection: 1
What is the animal's name? dog
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:3
```

```

1.- Register animals
2.- Free animals (all are set in the first shelter, the Stable.)
0.- Exit
Selection: 1
What is the animal's name? cat
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:4
1.- Register animals
2.- Free animals (all are set in the first shelter, the Stable.)
0.- Exit
Selection: 2
We have lost the animal with id 1!!!!
The animal with id 3 is at position [x=9, y=9].
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:3
Number of animals in the shelter Shelter2, position [x=9, y=9]:1
The animal with id 4 is at position [x=2, y=2].
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:2
Number of animals in the shelter Shelter2, position [x=9, y=9]:1
The animal with id 2 is at position [x=23, y=23].
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:1
The animal with id 3 is at position [x=13, y=13].
Number of animals in the shelter Stable, position [x=0, y=0]:0
The animal with id 4 is at position [x=10, y=10].
We have lost the animal with id 2!!!!
We have lost the animal with id 4!!!!
The animal with id 3 is at position [x=26, y=26].
The animal with id 3 is at position [x=8, y=8].
The animal with id 3 is at position [x=20, y=20].
Number of animals in the shelter Shelter4, position [x=20, y=20]:1
We have lost the animal with id 3!!!!
1.- Register animals
2.- Free animals (all are set in the first shelter, the Stable.)
0.- Exit
Selection: 0

```

Evaluation criteria

- Code quality:
 - Class, method and variable names are well used.
 - Clean code, correct indentation and clear methods.
- Correct execution:
 - Execution runs correctly if the user does what is requested.
- Exception handling:
 - The user enters Strings instead of numbers and the programme handles the exception properly.
- Use of the Observable Observer or PropertyChangeSupport pattern
 - Proper use of the Observable Observer or PropertyChangeSupport pattern and no use of println or scanner in other classes, except in Principal or Main.
 - Classes with appropriate content and correctly placed methods
- Encapsulation:
 - The structure of another class cannot be accessed and the possibility is given to overwrite them correctly via the toString method.

Create a file for each class with respective libraries. All notifications should be handled in the Main class based on the property change interface, and println must only be in the Main class. Main class should include the initialization, menu and propertychange interface to print all notifications of animal positions and shelters if animals are entered there, but not any extra methods. If additional methods to manage the system are required, then we should create a new class. Also, bear in mind that we can not access class attributes directly, we should have a getter or setter method if needed. Ensure execution is working.


```

>>>>>>>>>>Meat
Food Product [name=Sirloin, quantity=12, price=22.7] [type=Meat]
Food Product [name=Steak, quantity=5, price=1.7] [type=Meat]
Food Product [name=T-bone steak, quantity=3, price=12.7] [type=Meat]
1.- View all products classified in Food and Clothing
2.- View all products of foodtype fish and meat, sorted according to the quantity.
3.- View all clothing products sorted according to the size and price.
0.- Exit
Selection: 3
>>>>>>>>>>S
Clothing Product [name=Jacket, quantity=3, price=22.5] [size=S]
Clothing Product [name=Shirt, quantity=4, price=12.0] [size=S]
Clothing Product [name=t-shirt, quantity=4, price=10.0] [size=S]
Clothing Product [name=Socks, quantity=13, price=2.5] [size=S]
>>>>>>>>>>XL
Clothing Product [name=Trousers, quantity=2, price=50.0] [size=XL]
>>>>>>>>>>L
Clothing Product [name=Jumper, quantity=5, price=13.5] [size=L]
>>>>>>>>>>M
Clothing Product [name=Jacket, quantity=5, price=12.5] [size=M]
1.- View all products classified in Food and Clothing
2.- View all products of foodtype fish and meat, sorted according to the quantity.
3.- View all clothing products sorted according to the size and price.
0.- Exit
Selection: 0

```

Evaluation criteria

- Code quality:
 - Class, method and variable names are well used.
 - Clean code, correct indentation and clear methods.
- Correct execution:
 - Execution runs correctly if the user does what is requested.
- Exception handling:
 - The user enters Strings instead of numbers and the programme handles the exception properly.
- Use of the Observable Observer or PropertyChangeSupport pattern
 - Proper use of the Observable Observer or PropertyChangeSupport pattern and no use of println or scanner in other classes, except in Principal or Main.
 - Classes with appropriate content and correctly placed methods
- Adaptability:
 - Use of interfaces for the selection filtering of the products so that code is not repetitive (one method for each product selection)
 - Use of Factory Design pattern for the selection filtering.
- Encapsulation:
 - The structure of another class cannot be accessed, we should use getters or setters instead. Possibility to overwrite via toString, equals, hashCode and compareTo methods.
- Reusability:
 - Println only in the Main class
 - Classes with appropriate content and well-positioned methods.
- Collections:
 - Make use of maps and lists.

You should implement the following Selector Interface.

```
public interface Selector<T, V> {  
    V select(T value);  
}
```

You should develop a SelectorsFactory class. In this class you should have all the required selectors which implements Selector<T,V> from Selector interface, and you should @Override the select method. This should return a different V object based on the selector type. Implementation of sorting and filtering should be done using maps and lists in another more suitable class (not in the SelectorsFactory class). Do not use .collect method.

You must develop all the code and create a file for each class with respective libraries and all the necessary methods.

Exam 2

Q1

In light of the current situation, small shops in our country have sought assistance from the students and teachers at MGEP. With the rise of online stores, they have proposed the idea of creating an app to sell their products. However, they lack the resources to develop it on their own and have asked us to develop an initial version using Swing library in JAVA.

The main panel will display information about the various products available in the stores, including Quantity, Price, and Size (for clothing) or Type (for food).

The left panel will consist of three distinct sections:

- Price: This section will show the total price of all the products in the basket, indicating the amount the user needs to pay.
- Filters: In the central part, users can filter products based on three criteria:
- Product Type: Food or Clothing
- Food Type: Fish, Fruit, or Meat (if Food is selected)
- Size: S, M, L, XL (if Clothing is selected) After making their selections and pressing the "Search" button, the main panel will update to display products that match the selected criteria.
- Basket: This section will display the list of products that the user has added to their basket.

When a user selects a specific product, the selection will be highlighted in blue. If the selected product is available, the "Add to Basket" button will become active. Upon adding a product to the basket, a dialog box will appear showing the details of the product that has just been added. This product will then be listed in the Basket section, and the quantity of that product on the main panel will be reduced by one.

The user will be able to add as many products as they want to the basket. The total price of all the products in the basket will be continuously updated and displayed in the Price section at the top of the left panel.

Users will also have the option to remove products from the basket. When a product in the Basket section is selected, the "Drop-down" button will become active. Pressing this button will bring up a dialog showing the details of the product being removed from the basket. The total price will be updated accordingly, and the quantity of that product will be increased by one on the main panel.

The final option will be to complete the purchase. To do this, users will press the "Complete Purchase" button. This action will clear the items from the Basket, and a dialog will appear displaying the details of the entire purchase.

The following Initialisation method should we used to initialise products.

```
private void initialise() {
    plataform.add(new Clothing("Jacket", 5, 12.5, "M"));
    plataform.add(new Clothing("Jacket", 3, 22.5, "S"));
    plataform.add(new Clothing("Trousers", 2, 50, "XL"));
    plataform.add(new Clothing("Jumper", 5, 13.5, "L"));
    plataform.add(new Clothing("Socks", 13, 2.5, "S"));
    plataform.add(new Clothing("T-Shirt", 4, 10, "S"));
    plataform.add(new Clothing("Shirt", 4, 12, "S"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Sardines", 7, 5, "Fish"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Steak", 5, 1.7, "Meat"));
    plataform.add(new Food("T-bone Steak", 3, 12.7, "Meat"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Sirloin", 12, 22.7, "Meat"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Kiwie", 109, 2.4, "Fruit"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Apple", 24, 3.7, "Fruit"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Sea Bream", 4, 50.3, "Fish"));
    plataform.add(new Food("Hake", 6, 25, "Fish"));
}
```

Evaluation criteria:

- Code Quality
 - Class, method and variable names are well used.
 - Clean code, correct indentation and clear methods.
- Correct execution
 - Execution runs correctly with no errors and does what is requested.
- Graphic design
 - Graphic design is correct. It presents panels effectively, displaying all requested information, and using a Renderer if necessary.
- Use of Listeners
 - Utilize ActionListener or similars
- Structure of data
 - Use of appropriate Jlist models
- Encapsulation and reusability
 - The structure of another class cannot be accessed, we should use getters or setters instead.

Q2

The Basque Country Farmers Association has commissioned us to develop a Java application enabling farmers to track the location of their cattle continuously. The application consists of a Stable, several shelters and animals.

Through this application, we will release the animals into the field. Once each animal enters a shelter, they will remain inside. The application process will be considered complete when the last animal enters a Shelter.

Each animal will exhibit random movement while roaming freely in the field. Below, you'll find the code to simulate this.

In the application, all animals will initially begin in the Stable (this function is also provided). Therefore, when the app starts, all animals will be displayed on the "Shelter" Panel.

At the top of the panel, there will be a button. When this button is activated, the animals will be released from the Shelter and begin moving freely. Consequently, all animals will be transferred to the "Free" panel and displayed in the central panel, where they will move freely, each represented by its corresponding color. During this random movement, when an animal enters a shelter, it will stop and transition from the "field" panel back to the "Shelter" panel.

The app has a Central Panel with Shelters (black squares) and Animals (circled colors). Below is the initialisation method to initialise animals and shelters/stable:

```
private void initialise() {
    String name[]= {"Chicken1", "Chicken2", "Cat3", "Cat4", "Donkey5", "Donkey6",
    "Cow7", "Cow8"};
    int speed[] = {8,10,12,10,15,12,13,9};
    for(int i=0; i<name.length ;i++) {
        Animal animal =new Animal(name[i],i, speed[i], 300, 0,this);
        addAnimal(animal);
    }
}
```

Shelter and stable initialisation:

```
private void initialise() {
    system.add(new Shelter (1, "Stable",0,0));
    system.add(new Shelter (2, "Shelter1" ,250,200));
    system.add(new Shelter (3, "Shelter2" , 0,400));
    system.add(new Shelter (4, "Shelter3" , 500, 500));
}
```

Method to simulate animals movement:

```
public void move () {
    int dt;
    Random rd = new Random();
    dt = rd.nextInt(5);
    x= (int) (x+dt*vx);
    dt = rd.nextInt(10);
    y= (int) (y+dt*vy);
    .....
}
```

Evaluation criteria

- Code Quality
 - Class, method and variable names are well used

- Clean code, correct indentation and clear methods.
- Correct execution
 - Execution runs correctly with no errors and does what is requested.
- Graphic design
 - Graphic design is correct. It presents panels effectively, displaying all requested information, and using a Renderer if necessary.
- Use of Swing components/elements
 - Proper use of Swing components/elements. Use of appropriate Jlist models and renderers.
- Adaptability
 - Code easily adaptable and reusable
- Encapsulation
 - The structure of another class cannot be accessed, we should use getters or setters instead.

Software analysis and design

Exam

- Explain the incremental development process: its main characteristics and phases (1.5 points)
- What does the requirements elicitation phase consist of and what tasks does it include? (1.5 points)
- What are non-functional requirements? (1 point)
- What types and subtypes of non-functional requirements are there? Give an example of each of them (1 point)
- What is a stakeholder? Think of an example application and indicate its possible stakeholders (1 point)
- What is the ERS? What information does it include and what characteristics must it meet? (1 point)
- What is the activity diagram used for? (1 point)
- What is a scenario? Explain everything you know about scenarios. Give an example: write the scenario for a use case of an example application (1 point).
- Give an example of a state diagram and explain it (1 point).

Assignment

You must create a use case and write the ERS document for your application. Using the IEE830 standard as a reference, you should include functional requirements, non-functional requirements, use cases, scenarios, and an activity/state diagram. In addition, you must include ESRS with detailed diagrams.

Software engineering

Black box testing

Complete the table with only the minimum test cases to test all inputs in this application using black-box technique.

- Data type, Accepted values
- ID, 8 digits
- Colour, black, red, blue, orange, white
- Size, Between 30 and 65
- Quantity, <=10
- E-mail, At least 3 [a-z] @ at least 3 [a-z] . at least 2 [a-z]

White box testing

Implement the minimum test cases using white-box testing techniques to test 100% coverage. Add the "?" character when it does not matter if it is true or false.

```
if {(A or B) and (C or D) and (E or F)} then
Statement1
else
statement2
```

Static Analysis

- Calculate the cyclomatic Complexity of this function
- Calculate the Maximum Nesting of Control Structure value of the same function
- Calculate the Knot Count value of the same function
- Calculate the Number of Local Variables of the same function
- Calculate the number of Logical operators of the same function

```
void fiboFunction()
{
    long int Fibo, tmp, FiboAurrekoa, z;
    int kont;
    char str[128];

    Fibo = 2;
    FiboAurrekoa = 1;
    for (kont = 3; kont <= 20; kont++){
        z = 2;
        while ( Fibo % z != 0 && z <= Fibo/2){
            z++;
        }
    }
}
```

```

    }
    if (z > Fib0/2){
        printf("%3d: %d \n", kont, Fib0);
    }
    else{
        printf("%3d: %d \n", kont, Fib0);
    }
    tmp = Fib0;
    Fib0 = Fib0 + Fib0Aurrekoa;
    Fib0Aurrekoa = tmp;
}
}

```

What values must you include to each variable to test this function and obtain a 100% coverage using the minimum Test Cases?

```

public void function1(int s, int m, int h){
    s++;
    if (s == 60)
    {
        s = 0;
        m=m+1;
    }

    if (m == 60) {
        m = 0;
        h=h+1;
    }

    if (h == 24) {
        h = 0;
    }
}

```

What would you include into the @Test parentheses if you want to test someFunction function?

```

@Test(      )

public void _____ {
}

public int someFunction() {
    int total= 0;
    for(int i=0; i>=0; i++){
        total = total + i;
    }
    return total;
}

```

Testing concept exercises

Given: Python, Java, JS, PHP, C#, Ruby, C++, Scala and Node

Black box testing. Taking into account the image values, which is not the valid programming language?

- Scala
- Pascal
- PHP
- Python

```
Given: if (n<0)
      n=0;
      if (q==3)
          i=z+5;
      else
          i=z-2;
```

Which values must be used to obtain a 100\% coverage?

- n = 1 && q = 3; n = 0 && q = 6;
- n = -9 && q = 2; n = -1 && q = 3;
- n = 0 && q = 3; n = -1 && q = 5;
- n = 0 && q = 4; n = -6 && q = 2;

What is not a black box testing advantage?

- Code access is not required
- Limited coverage since only a fraction of test scenarios is performed
- Separation between user's and developer's perspectives
- Efficient for large segments of code

What is a code smell?

- all answers are incorrect
- an issue affecting your maintainability rating
- an issue highlighting a security hole that can be used to attack software
- an issue highlighting a real or potential point of failure in your software

Decision Coverage is ...

- Both are false
- At least one result true and one false
- Both are true
- At least one condition true and one false

When a test suite is defined, what tag must be included?

- @Suite
- @SuiteClasses
- @TestSuite
- @Test

What are mocks?

- Objects that compare real results with the expected results
- Functions that compare real results with the expected results
- Objects that simulate the behavior of the real objects
- Functions that simulate the behavior of other functions

createStrictMock...

- creates a mock and also takes care of the order of method calls
- creates a mock for some functions, a mock is not created for all the class
- creates a mock which returns default values for methods not overridden
- creates mocks without bothering about the order of method calls

What is a stub?

- It is a test conducted to determine if the requirements of a specification or contract are met
- It is a piece of code used to stand in for some other programming functionality
- It is testing conducted on a complete integrated system to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements
- It is re-running methods to ensure that previously developed and tested software still performs after a change

What is acceptance testing?

- It is a test conducted to determine if the requirements of a specification or contract are met
- It is re-running functional and non-functional tests to ensure that previously developed and tested software still performs after a change
- It is testing conducted on a complete integrated system to evaluate the system's compliance with its specified requirements
- It is a software testing method by which individual units of source code

Unitary testing exercise

Test the exam function using parameters and the following structure to check different values: `//public static Collection<Object[]> numbers() {return Arrays.asList(new Object[][] {});`

`package exam;`

```

public class exam1 {

    public static boolean exam(int n){
        int i,m=0;
        boolean flag=true;
        m=oneHalf(n);
        if(n==0||n==1){
            flag=false;
        }else{
            for(i=2;i<=m;i++){
                if(getRestZero(n,i)){
                    flag=false;
                    break;
                }
            }
        }
        return flag;
    }

    static boolean getRestZero(int a, int b) {
        return a % b == 0;
    }

    public static int oneHalf (int n) {
        return n/2;
    }

}

```

Mocks testing exercise

Test the exam function using Easymock's partialmock and imagine that "oneHalf" and "getRestZero" are under development

```

package exam;

public class exam1 {

    public static boolean exam(int n){
        int i,m=0;
        boolean flag=true;
        m=oneHalf(n);
        if(n==0||n==1){
            flag=false;
        }else{
            for(i=2;i<=m;i++){
                if(getRestZero(n,i)){
                    flag=false;
                    break;
                }
            }
        }
        return flag;
    }

    static boolean getRestZero(int a, int b) {
        return a % b == 0;
    }

    public static int oneHalf (int n) {
        return n/2;
    }

}

```

Test suite exercise

Create a TestSuite to run both tests

Refactoring

Refactor the following two functions

```
public class Customer {
    private String name;
    private List<Order> orders;

    public void printOwing() {
        double outstanding = 0.0;

        // print banner
        System.out.println("*****");
        System.out.println("***** Customer Owes *****");
        System.out.println("*****");

        // calculate outstanding
        for (Order order : orders) {
            outstanding += order.getAmount();
        }

        // print details
        System.out.println("name: " + name);
        System.out.println("amount: " + outstanding);
    }
}

public class Customer {
    private String name;
    private List<Order> orders;

    public void printOwing() {
        printBanner();
        double outstanding = calculateOutstanding();
        printDetails(outstanding);
    }

    private void printBanner() {
        System.out.println("*****");
        System.out.println("***** Customer Owes *****");
        System.out.println("*****");
    }

    private double calculateOutstanding() {
        double outstanding = 0.0;
        for (Order order : orders) {
            outstanding += order.getAmount();
        }
        return outstanding;
    }

    private void printDetails(double outstanding) {
        System.out.println("name: " + name);
        System.out.println("amount: " + outstanding);
    }
}
```

Theory questionnaire

Which command is used to upload all commits and objects performed?

- fetch
- pull
- clone
- push

What is .gitignore?

- It is a command to avoid file, dir or patterns to be included at the stage
- It is a file to avoid file, dir or patterns to be included at the stage
- It is an special repository to avoid file, dir or patterns to be included at the stage
- It is a folder to avoid file, dir or patterns to be included at the stage

The develop branch is ...

- the main branch in which the latest delivered development changes for the next release
- the branch where the source code always reflects a production-ready state
- a branch used to develop new characteristics for the upcoming release
- a branch created to solve critical bugs

The branch command ...

- creates a new branch and adds a new tag
- creates a new branch
- switches to the specified branch and updates the working directory adding a new tag
- switches to the specified branch and updates the working directory

¿What are the branches?

- Comments in the historic evolution of a code
- A command to check the status of the project
- Set of changes that differ from the main line of the development
- A new development performed by a programmer

The commit command ...

- changes files from the working directory to the stage
- changes files from the working directory to the repository

- changes files from the stage to the repository
- changes files from the stage to the working directory

How should we use commit?

- All answers are correct
- Commits of changes that are a logical change (if not, better smaller commits)
- Do not commit unfinished changes. Ideally only commits from code that works perfectly
- Commit frequently. The smaller and more frequent that commits are, the better (for integration, review, test, etc.).

Remote commands are ...

- clone, remote, merge, pull and push
- commit, remote, fetch, pull and push
- clone, remote, fetch, pull and push
- clone, fetch, pull and push

HEAD is ...

- a pointer to the local branch you are currently on
- the origin/master branch
- the branch by default
- the name of a new branch

Which of the following statements is true for centralized version control?

- All statements are true
- Programmers commit their changes to this central copy.
- Commits affect the main repository and all computer connected in a single step
- There is more than one copy even the main one is in the central repository

Which is the command to initialize Git on the current folder?

Set the user name for the current repository to:

```
git config --global XXXXXXXX "studentA"
```

The command to include a new file in the repository

```
git XXXXXXXX "index.html"
```

Include the changes to the current repository

```
git XXXXX YYYYYYYY "First release!"
```

Command to include a "tag" pointing to the current commit

```
git XXXXXXXXXXX "version1.0"
```

Git command to list all the existing branches

```
git XXXXXXXXXXXXX
```

Git command to "checkout" a branch with the current branch

```
git XXXXXXXXXXXXX iss001
```

pull is a combination between

```
First XXXXXXXXXXXX and thenYYYYYYYYYY
```

Git command to upload the current branch to the remote repository with all the necessary commits and objects

```
git XXXXXXXXXXXXX origin
```

Git command to download the remote repository to the local repository the first time

```
git XXXXXXXXXXXXX https://abc.com/x/y.git
```